

Effects of Packaging Material and Storage Duration on Germination Ability and Vigour of Stored Sunflower Seeds

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Abstract

This study was conducted at Sokoine University of Agriculture, Tanzania, to examine the impact of interaction between packaging materials, seed sources, and storage duration on the viability and vigour of sunflower seeds. Quality Declared Seeds (QDS), certified seeds (Control), and farmer-saved seeds were stored in three types of packaging—plastic containers, polypropylene bags, and sisal bags—over six months. Monthly assessments were conducted to measure seed moisture content (SMC), germination percentage (GeP), seedling vigour index (SVI), and fungal infection incidence (FII), using a split-split-plot design in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The results revealed highly significant interaction effects of packaging materials and storage duration on all parameters ($P < 0.001$). Before storage, seeds exhibited a minimum SMC of 9.00%, a maximum GeP of 87.0%, an SVI of 1981.6, and a low FII of 44%. After six months, seeds stored in plastic containers maintained the highest GeP (80.22%), SVI (1814), and the lowest FII (64.17%) and SMC (10.22%). In contrast, seeds in sisal bags recorded the lowest GeP (68.89%), SVI (1536), highest FII (74.33%), and SMC (13.14%). The combination effects of packaging materials, seed sources, and storage duration were significantly different for SMC ($P = 0.014$) and FII ($P < 0.001$), while no significant interaction was found for GeP ($P = 0.677$) and SVI ($P = 0.584$). This study highlights that plastic containers are the most effective packaging for preserving sunflower seed viability and vigour, while reducing fungal infections. It underscores the significance of proper packaging and storage strategies to enhance seed quality, crucial for improving sunflower productivity in Tanzania.

Keywords: *Fungi, moisture content, viability, seedling vigour, packaging material, seed sources..*

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Introduction

The production of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) crop is solely dependent on true-seed as the only means of propagation. Hence, good quality sunflower seed is a critical agricultural input that affects crop productivity as well as production. In Tanzania, previous researches show that over 90% of the seeds used by farmers come from informal (farmer saved seeds) and semi-formal (Quality declared seeds) seed supply systems (BOT, 2017 and Tibamanya et al., 2022). However, low seed viability of seeds produced under these systems is a major challenge associated with poor seed storage practices including inadequate packaging materials at the farm level, which hampers the availability of quality seeds to smallholder farmers (Sperling et al., 2021).

At physiological maturity, sunflower seed reaches the maximum capability of its germination and vigour potential. The type of seed packaging materials has a substantial impact on seed viability and vigour (Hasan et al., 2017). It is crucial to preserve the seed's viability and vigour for a long period.

Similar to other crops, one of the major obstacles to sunflower crop cultivation is the lack of seeds which are highly viable and vigorous at the period of propagating. This is because in most cases the seeds drop their germinating capability and energy before the next crop sowing term due to inappropriate seed preserving managements, like usage of unsuitable packaging materials and storage settings (Hedimbi et al., 2012). Singh et al. (2000) discovered that five to seventeen percentage can be lost in seed germination due to improper seed handling actions including storage activities.

Farmers and seed dealers in Tanzania typically use polypropylene bags to carry and store their seeds for bulk storage and for transportation as well. Gebeyaw, (2020) stated that, seed can easily become infected by biotic organisms because these packaging materials are not suitable for protecting them from infestation by microorganisms. It is also evident that the majority of the small-holder farmers in the country are unaware of and uninformed about the necessary seed storage procedures as found by Kimario et al. (2022) and Makundi et al. (2022). Thus, seed quality is substantially influenced by seed management techniques (Mwanishi and Msuya, 2023). To protect the seed from losing its viability and vigour, it is a good idea to use the proper packaging materials.

Hasan et al.'s (2017) research on lentil seeds revealed that seeds stored in sealed containers with minimal moisture content retained higher seed quality characteristics when compared to other packaging materials utilized in the study. Furthermore, Suleiman et al. (2013) noted that because seed is an extremely hygroscopic organisms, it will absorb water from the air when preserved in surroundings where air-relative humidity levels are greater than the seed's moisture content.

When seeds are stored in areas with limited air movement, heat accumulations from respiration cause the seeds to lose quality as described by Bareke, (2018). Therefore proper storage is a basic requirement. Through storage, the seed should be highly protected against pathogens and pests. Various seed packaging materials like air-tight tin bin regulate the temperature, relative humidity, and moisture levels of stored seeds, according to Nyo et al. (2019).

The objective of this research is to assess the impact of different seed packaging materials on the viability and vigour of sunflower seeds stored under ambient conditions. The Null Hypothesis (H_0) posits that there is no significant difference in the viability and vigour of sunflower seeds stored under ambient conditions when packaged in different materials (plastic containers, polypropylene bags, and sisal bags) across the three types of seeds (Quality Declared Seeds, certified seeds, and farmer saved seeds) over the six-month storage period. In Tanzania, there is limited studies on the best packaging materials for sunflower seeds thus, it is challenging to decide which materials are appropriate for storing sunflowers because of this. Therefore, the current research aimed at assessing how the interaction effect of seed source, packaging materials and storage duration influence the viability and vigour of sunflower seeds under storage. Polypropylene bags, sisal bags, and plastic containers were selected due to their availability.

Ultimately, the study seeks to identify the best packaging materials for seed storage within informal and semi-formal systems.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Seed Material

Sunflower seed samples which are Quality Declared Seeds (QDS), certified Open Pollinated Variety(OPV) and Farmer saved seeds (FSS) collected in growing season 2022/2023 from Sunflower QDS producers, Agricultural Seed Agency (ASA) and farmers respectively were used. Three different packaging materials namely plastic containers, polypropylene bags and sisal bags were used for storing the seeds. The seeds were naturally air-dried until they had a moisture content of 9% as it is a currently a recommended moisture content for short term storage periods (Sisman and Delibas, 2004). The determination of seed moisture content involved a high temperature oven technique.

Seed Storage

This storage laboratory experiment was conducted at Sokoine University of Agriculture, Department of Crop Science and Horticulture in African Seed Health Centre Laboratory in Morogoro Tanzania.

1.5 kilogram of each seed sources were packed separately in plastic containers, polypropylene bags and sisal bags. The polypropylene and sisal bags were carefully stitched using strings, and the plastic containers were snugly closed with their plastic coverings (Figure 1A). Samples were then stored in lab at African Seed Health Centre without control of storage conditions (temperature and relative humidity) for a duration of six months from December, 2022 to June, 2023.

After that, the seeds in their respective packaging materials were put in the laboratory for ambient-preserving. For assessing seed viability, seed vigour, seed health, and moisture content assessments, seed samples were taken on a monthly basis. Before storage the sunflower seeds were tested on germination percentage, seedling vigour and fungal infestation and infection according to ISTA, (2022) guidelines in order to discover their initial quality.

Figure 1. Storage Experiment in the Lab (A); Monthly Mean Temperature and Relative Humidity during Experimentation (B)

During experimentation, the temperature varied from 21.3 °C to 27.5 °C recorded in the fifth and third month of storage respectively. The relative humidity during the experiment ranged from 74.1% to 88%.

The highest RH (88%) was observed in the fifth month while the smallest Relative humidity (74.1%) was recorded in the third month of experimentation (Figure 1B).

Experimental Design

Experimental factors were Sunflower seeds (3 sources);—QDS, certified OPV (Control) and FSS and packaging materials (3 types)—plastic containers, polypropylene bags and sisal bags and six storage durations (Month 1 to 6). The Storage trial was a split split-plot set-out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) replicated 3 times whereby packaging materials were the main-plots, sources of seeds were sub-plots while the storage duration was a sub-sub plot.

Collected Data

Seed Moisture Content (%)

The seed moisture content obtained by means of a Constant Temperature Oven technique, where a portion of 10g from the sample was used replicated twice in petri dishes with 8 cm diameter. The mass of empty petri dish was measured and recorded as M1, then the petri dish was measured with the seeds and its cover and recorded as M2, the dishes' contained seeds were placed in oven at $103\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a duration of 17 hours, then at 105°C till constant weight, after 30 minutes of cooling by a desiccator, the petri dishes were quickly measured and the mass recorded as M3 (ISTA, 2022)

The following formula (1) was used to determine the seed moisture contents (MC%)

$$MC (\%) = \frac{M2-M3}{M3-M2} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where;

MC = Moisture Content (%)

M1 = the weight (g) of empty petri dish plus its cover

M2 = the weight (g) of dish, its cover plus seeds before drying.

M3 = the weight (g) of dish, its cover plus seeds after drying.

Germination Test

In four replications, 200 seedlings from each treatment were selected and subjected to the standard germination test. By planting the seedlings in germination bowls with sterile sand soil, the test was evaluated. To maintain the requisite soil moisture, irrigation was carried out as needed usually in the morning and in the evening. Starting on the seeding date and continuing for 10 days, germination was checked daily.

Ajayi and Fakorede's, (2000) formula (2) was used to calculate the germination percentages of typical seedlings;

$$Germination \% = \frac{Number\ of\ germinated\ seeds}{Total\ number\ of\ seeds\ sown} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

Seedling Vigour Index

On the tenth day, all healthy seedlings which were considered to be strong seedlings were chosen. The seedling length of 15 seedlings was measured using a ruler and so used to compute the seedling vigour index via the equation (3) by Abdul-Baki and Anderson (1973) below.

$$\text{Seedling vigour index} = \text{Germination (\%)} \cdot \text{seedling length (cm)} \quad (3)$$

Fungal Seed Contamination

As one of the biotic factors, seed health test on fungal incidence on stored sunflower seeds was also performed. 200 of seeds from respective samples were sown in petri-dishes monthly, 10 seeds per dish using blotter papers. Before plating, sunflower seeds were first immersed into a solution of sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl_2) in 5 minutes then rinsed-thrice in sterile water for 3 minutes. Then the cultures were kept at room temperature for 7 days of alternating cycle of light (12 hours) and darkness (12 hours). On the 8th day seeds were inspected using a stereomicroscope to observe the growth of fungus. Further observation of fungal conidia and conidiomata were made through compound microscope in slides.

Mathur and Kongsdal's (2003) book Common Laboratory Seed Health Testing Methods for Detecting Fungi was used as a guide for identifying the various fungal species.

Ghiasian *et al.*, (2004) equation (4) below was used to get fungal infection incidence:

$$\text{Infection incidence (\%)} = \frac{\text{No.of seeds infected by fungus}}{\text{Total number of seeds}} \cdot 100\% \quad (4)$$

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using a three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to investigate the main and interactive effects of packaging materials, seed sources and storage duration (three main fixed effects) on seed moisture content (%), germination percentage, seedling vigour index and fungal infection incidence (%). Environmental conditions (particularly temperature & humidity) and Replicates were treated as random effects. With mixed model. The statistical analyses all followed by Tukey's post-hoc multiple comparisons ($P < 0.05$) by GenStat Discovery Statistical Package of the 16th version. A value of $P < 0.05$ was regarded statistically significant and a value of $P < 0.01$ was considered highly significant. OriginLab Origin (2022) software was used to draw figures. Tables were created using Excel, 2019.

Results

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to evaluate the effects of packaging materials, seed source, and storage duration on four measured variables: germination percentage, seed moisture content, seedling vigour index, and fungal infection incidence. Below is the summarized explanations for results of the main effects (Table 1 & 2):

Table 1. ANOVA Table of Results for Packaging Materials, Seed Source and Storage Time on Seed Moisture Content (%), Germination Percentage, Seedling Vigour Index and Fungal Infection Incidence (%)

	Measured variable				
		Germination percentage	Seed Moisture Content (%)	Seedling vigour index	Fungal infection incidence (%)
Source of variation	d.f.	F pr.			
Main plot Analysis					
Packaging materials	2	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
Subplot Analysis					
Seed source	2	<.001	0.171	<.001	<.001
Sub-sub plot analysis					
Storage duration	6	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
Packaging x Storage duration	12	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
Seed source x Storage duration	12	0.017	0.287	0.339	<.001
Packaging x Seed source x Storage duration	24	0.677	0.014	0.584	<.001

Note: d.f., degrees of freedom; F pr., test-F probability.

Main Plot Analysis: Packaging Materials

The study highlights that packaging materials significantly impact various aspects of seed performance, with all variables tested—germination percentage, seed moisture content, seedling vigour index, and fungal infection incidence—showing highly significant differences ($P < 0.001$). This indicates that the choice of packaging plays a crucial role in enhancing germination rates, maintaining moisture levels, promoting seedling health, and reducing the incidence of fungal infections in seeds.

Subplot Analysis: Seed Source

The analysis reveals that seed sources significantly influenced germination potential and seedling vigour index, with both variables showing highly significant differences ($P < 0.001$). Additionally, there are notable variations in susceptibility to fungal infections among different seed sources. However, seed moisture content among the seed sources showed no significant differences, with values clustered around 10.06% with a P -value of 0.171, indicating consistent moisture retention across the various seed types.

Sub-sub Plot Analysis: Storage Duration

All measured variables showed highly significant effects ($P < 0.001$) with storage duration, indicating that the length of time seeds stored significantly influenced germination, moisture content, vigour, and fungal infection rates.

Table 2. Effects of Packaging Material and Seed Sources on Seed Moisture Content, Germination (%), Germination Index, Seedling Vigour Index and Fungal Incidence on Sunflower Seeds Stored under Ambient Conditions

Treatment	Moisture content (%)	Germination percentage	Seedling vigour index	Fungal infection (%)
P-materials				
P1	9.44a	84.05a	1905a	52.87a
P2	10.11b	81.83b	1841b	56.93b
P3	10.64c	78.87c	1759c	60.75c
Mean	10.064	81.58	1834.9	56.852
SE	0.00913	0.251	5.9	0.1003

CV%	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.3
P-value	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
S-sources				
S1	10.06a	88.19a	2000a	54.64a
S2	10.05a	87.56a	1979a	54.46a
S3	10.09a	69b	1526b	61.45b
SE	0.01357	0.227	5.7	0.1692
Mean	10.064	81.58	1834.9	56.852
CV%	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.3
P-value	0.171	<.001	<.001	<.001

Note: Where P-Packaging materials, P1=Plastic container, P2=Polypropylene bags and P3=sisal bags; S-Seed sources, S1=certified seed, S2=QDS and S3=Farm saved seeds. SE=standard error of means and CV=coefficients of variation. Each data point was based on four samples. The means with the same letter(s) in the same column imply non-significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ due to Tukey's 95% confidence intervals.

Interaction Effects

Interaction effects of packaging material and storage duration on seed moisture content (%), germination percentage, seedling vigour index and fungal infection incidence (%)

The analysis in Table 1 reveals a significant interaction ($P < .001$) between packing materials and storage duration on seed moisture content. Initially measured at 9.00%, seed moisture content increased markedly to 13.14% by the fifth month in seeds stored in sisal bags. However, a slight decrease was observed in the sixth month, with seeds in plastic containers showing a moisture content of 10.22%, followed closely by those in polypropylene bags at 12.08% (Figure 2A).

Nonetheless, a significant interaction effect between packaging materials and storage duration was identified on seed germination percentage ($P < 0.001$), as shown in Table 1. The germination rates across different packaging materials were influenced by the duration of storage, with a noticeable decline over time (Figure 2B). By the end of the sixth month, seeds stored in plastic containers exhibited the highest germination percentage at 80.22%, followed by those in polypropylene bags at 74.44%, and sisal bags at 68.89%.

Furthermore, a significant interaction effect between packaging materials and storage duration was observed on the seedling vigour index ($P < 0.001$), as detailed in Table 1. The seedling vigour index varied with storage duration and packaging type. Notably, seeds stored in plastic containers demonstrated a substantially higher vigour index of 1814, compared to 1672 for polypropylene bags and 1536 for sisal bags (Figure 2C).

The combined effects of packaging materials and storage duration significantly influenced fungal infection incidence ($P < 0.001$), as indicated in Table 1. The incidence of fungal infection varied with storage duration and the type of packaging used. Starting from an initial infection percentage of 44%, the incidence rose over time, peaking at 74.33% in seeds stored in sisal bags, followed by 68.61% in polypropylene bags, and the lowest incidence recorded at 64.17% in seeds packed in plastic containers (Figure 2D).

Various fungal species, including *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Aspergillus* species, *Alternaria spp.*, and *Curvularia lunata*, were identified in different packaging materials during storage (Figure 2E).

Figure 2. Effects of Interaction of Packaging Material and Storage Duration to Moisture Content (A), Germination Percentage (B), Seedling Vigour Index (C), Fungal Infection Incidence (D), Interaction Effect of Packaging Materials and Fungal Species ($P < 0.001$) on Fungal Infection Incidence, (E) on Sunflower Seeds Stored under Ambient Conditions. The Means with the Same Letter(s) are Not Different ($P \leq 0.05$) due to Tukey's 95% Confidence Intervals. Each Data Point was Based on Four Samples. M0-M6 =Month 0 to Month 6, M0 = Initial Seed Testing. P1=Plastic Container, P2=Polypropylene Bags and P3=Sisal Bags, The Number of Samples Taken were Four per Data Point

Interaction effects of packaging material and seed source on seed moisture content (%), germination percentage, seedling vigour index and fungal infection incidence (%)

The analysis revealed no significant interactions between packaging materials and seed sources regarding seed moisture content ($P=0.213$), seed germination ($P=0.979$), or seedling vigour index ($P=0.993$) (Table 3).

The interaction between packaging materials and seed sources had a significant impact on fungal seed-borne infection in stored sunflower seeds ($P<0.001$) (Table 3). Notably, farmer-saved seeds (S3) packed in sisal bags (P3) exhibited the highest fungal infection percentage at 65.21%, compared to those stored in plastic container and polypropylene bags at 60.38%. (Table 3). This suggested that sisal bags might be less effective in preventing fungal growth compared to plastic or polypropylene bags.

Table 3. Interaction Effects of Packaging Material and Seed Sources on Moisture Content, Seedling Vigour Index and Fungal Incidence on Sunflower Seeds Stored under Ambient Conditions

Treatment (Pm x Ss)	Moisture content (%)	Germination percentage	Seedling vigour index	Fungal infection (%)
P1 S1	9.43a	90.57a	2069a	50.14a
P2 S1	10.11b	88.38b	2003b	55.21b
P3 S1	10.64c	85.62c	1927c	58.57c
P1 S2	9.45a	90a	2050a	49.71a
P2 S2	10.10b	87.9b	1986b	55.19b
P3 S2	10.59c	84.76c	1902c	58.48c
P1 S3	9.43a	71.57d	1597d	58.76c
P2 S3	10.13b	69.19e	1533e	60.38d
P3 S3	10.7c	66.24f	1448f	65.21e
Mean	10.064	81.58	1834.9	56.85
CV%	0.4	0.5	0.9	0.9
P-value	0.213	0.979	0.993	<0.001

Note: Where Pm=Packaging materials; P1=Plastic container, P2=Polypropylene bags and P3=sisal bags; Ss=Seed sources; S1=certified seed, S2=QDS and S3=Farm saved seeds. SE=standard error of means and CV=coefficients of variation. The means with the same letter(s) in the same column imply non-significantly different at $P\leq 0.05$ due to Tukey's 95% confidence intervals.

Interaction effects of seed source and storage duration on Seed moisture content (%), germination percentage, seedling vigour index and fungal infection incidence (%):

There was no significant interaction between seed source and storage duration for seed moisture content ($P=0.287$), as shown in Table 1. However, the combination effect of seed source and storage duration was significantly different for seed germination percentage ($P=0.017$). The germination percentage decreased with increasing storage duration across different seed sources. By the end of the fourth month, both the control and QDS seed sources recorded germination rates of 86.89% and 86.0%, respectively, remaining above the minimum germination percentage stipulated by Tanzania Official Certification Institute (TOSCI) regulations (Figure 3B).

In contrast, the combination effect of seed sources and storage periods did not show significant differences for the seedling vigour index ($P=0.339$) (Table 1). However, the interaction effect between seed sources and storage duration was highly significant for fungal infection incidence ($P<0.001$) (Table 1). By the end of the sixth month, the QDS source exhibited the lowest fungal infection rate at 66.94%,

closely followed by the certified seeds (control) at 67.06%, while the FSS source recorded the highest infection rate at 73.11% (Figure 3D).

Figure 3. Effects of Interaction of Source of Seeds and Storage Duration to Moisture Content (A), Germination Percentage (B), Seedling Vigour Index (C), Fungal Infection Incidence (D) on Sunflower Seeds Stored under Ambient Conditions. The Means with the Same Letter(s) are not Different ($P \leq 0.05$) due to Tukey's 95% Confidence Intervals. Each Data Point was Based on Four Samples. M0-M6 =Month 0 to Month 6, M0 = Initial Seed Testing (Used as Control). S1=Certified Seed, S2=QDS and S3=Farm Saved Seeds

Interaction between packaging materials, seed source and storage durations on seed moisture content (%), germination percentage, seedling vigour index and fungal infection incidence (%)

Table 1 indicates that the interaction between packaging materials, seed source, and storage duration significantly affected seed moisture content ($P=0.014$). The moisture content of the seeds was found to vary depending on the type of packaging and the duration of storage. This suggests that the combined effect of these three factors is important for moisture retention. By the end of the sixth month, the minimum seed moisture content (SMC) was observed in QDS (10.167%) and certified seeds (10.181%), both stored in plastic containers. In contrast, the maximum moisture content was recorded in FSS seeds stored in sisal bags (13.044%), followed by those in polypropylene bags (12.226%) (Figure 4A).

The ANOVA results further revealed that the interaction effect of packaging materials, seed source, and storage duration was not significant for germination percentage ($P=0.677$) and seedling vigour index ($P=0.584$) (Table 1). This means that the combined effect of all involved factors was less influential on germination and vigour. However, the combined effects of packaging materials, seed sources, and storage duration were significantly different concerning fungal infection incidence ($P<0.001$) (Table 1). This implies that the interaction effect of these three factors is vital for fungal resistance. This effect was found to depend on the type of packaging materials and the initial health status of the seeds. Farm-saved seeds packed in sisal bags exhibited the highest fungal infection incidence at 79.5%, while certified seeds (the control) and QDS in plastic containers showed the lowest incidences at 62.5% and 61.5%, respectively, by the end of the sixth month (Figure 4B).

Figure 4. Effects of Interaction of Packaging Material, Source of Seeds and Storage Duration to Moisture Content (A), Germination Percentage (B), Seedling Vigour Index (D), Fungal Infection Incidence(%) (E) on Sunflower Seeds Stored under Ambient Conditions. The Means with the Same Letter(s) are Not Different ($P \leq 0.05$) due to Tukey's 95% Confidence Intervals. Each Data Point was Based on Four Samples. M0-M6 =Month 0 to Month 6, M0 = Initial Seed Testing (Used as Control). P1=Plastic Container, P2=Polypropylene Bags and P3=Sisal Bags. S1=Certified Seed, S2=QDS and S3=Farm Saved Seeds

Discussion

Interaction Effects of Packaging Material and Storage Duration

The variations in seed moisture content observed among different packaging materials over time can be attributed to the differing permeability of these materials. Among the materials tested, plastic containers were found to be the least permeable, minimizing moisture exchange with the external environment, a finding supported by Sumathi (2010). The marked increase in moisture content over storage duration, particularly in seeds stored in sisal bags, suggests that this material may not effectively protect against moisture absorption, which can compromise seed quality. Seeds are hygroscopic, leading to moisture exchange in porous packaging under high relative humidity (Delouche et al., 2021; Karunakaran et al., 2001).

The decline in germination rates over time observed, emphasizes that prolonged storage adversely affects seed viability. Tandoh et al. (2017) noted similar trends in *Pericopsis elata* seeds. Plastic containers performed best, retaining the highest germination rate, which may be attributed to their ability to limit moisture ingress and reduce exposure to environmental stressors compared to polypropylene and sisal bags. Sultana et al. (2016) found plastic packaging to be most effective for storing okra seeds. Hedimbi et al. (2012) showed that barley seeds-maintained viability and vigour when stored in plastic packaging at low temperatures (4°C) over a 16-month period, outperforming other materials. In research by Adam et al. (2018), cowpea seeds stored in plastic containers achieved the highest germination percentages compared to those in aluminum bags and envelopes.

Similar trends were noted here, with plastic containers supporting greater seedling vigour. This is crucial for ensuring robust seedling development, which can ultimately influence crop yield. Variations in the seedling vigour index were likely influenced by differences in germination rates and seedling lengths, which were the key components in its calculation. This finding aligns with other studies, such as those by Vange et al. (2016) in soybean and Patel et al. (2018) in chickpea. Tandoh (2017) and Meena et al. (2017) observed similar patterns of reduced seedling vigour with increased storage duration in *Pericopsis elata* and cotton seeds respectively. Del Rosario et al. (2017) reported similar findings regarding the seedling vigour index of rice, which varied significantly across different packaging materials after four months of storage. The current study's results corroborate previous research on chickpea, and lentil seeds conducted by Chormule et al. (2015) and Hasan et al. (2017).

The significant rise in fungal infection over time, especially in seeds stored in sisal bags, underscores the need for effective packaging to mitigate fungal threats during storage. The presence of various fungal species highlights the risks associated with improper storage conditions.

Interaction Effects of Packaging Material and Seed Source

The analysis revealed no significant interactions between packaging materials and seed sources for seed moisture content, germination percentage, or seedling vigour index, suggesting that the effects of packaging and seed source do not significantly influence these variables when combined.

However, the significant interaction found concerning fungal infection incidence suggests that the impact of packaging material on fungal infections varies significantly depending on the seed source (Mohapatra et al., 2017). Notably, farmer-saved seeds packed in sisal bags showed the highest infection indicated that this combination might create a conducive environment for fungal growth. In contrast, certified and QDS seeds stored in plastic containers exhibited the lowest infection rate (Johnson, 2019; Kwaloe et al., 2018 and Lavkor & Var, 2017). This highlights the importance of both seed quality and packaging material in managing seed health, particularly under ambient storage conditions (Odokonyero et al., 2021 and Ogwu et al., 2024).

Interaction Effects of Seed Source and Storage Duration

While there was no significant interaction for seed moisture content, the germination percentage showed a significant interaction, indicating that seed source and storage duration jointly influence germination rates. The variations in germination percentages could primarily be due to initial seed quality differences. Shelar et al. (2008) emphasized that seed quality and viability during storage are closely linked to the initial quality of the seeds and their storage conditions. Farm-saved seeds (FSS) had the lowest initial germination rate (75%) compared to certified seeds (92%) and QDS (94%), highlighting the importance of using improved seed varieties. Over time, germination percentages declined, a trend observed in several crop species. For instance, Genes and Nyomora (2018) found a decrease in germination percentages of *Excoecaria bussei* seeds as storage duration increased. Similar findings were reported by Aladele et al. (2020) in okra and Fu et al. (2018) in peanut kernels, Nataraj & Jayaramgowda (2017); Tame & Elam (2015) in soybean seeds, Islam et al. (2017) in mungbean and Adam et al. (2018) in cowpeas. The fact that both the control and Quality Declared Seeds (QDS) maintained high germination percentages through four months is promising, but raises concerns as storage duration increases.

Conversely, the interaction effect on seedling vigour index was not significant suggesting that factors other than seed source and storage duration may be more influential in determining seed vigour. However, the interaction concerning fungal infection incidence was significant, with farmer-saved seeds exhibiting the highest rates of infection. Furthermore, numerous studies have indicated that most fungal species negatively impact the viability and vigour of stored seeds by accelerating deterioration. According to Abd-El-Aziz and El-Satar (2016) and Hatim et al. (2022), microorganisms from storage environments, such as *Aspergillus* and *Alternaria* species, can lead to root collar rot, compromised root-shoot systems, damping off in seedlings, and seed rot, all of which diminish seed viability and vigour. *Fusarium* species, including *F. moniliforme*, have been reported to cause stunting, seedling blight, wilting, and foot rot, which are prominent symptoms in sunflower and other crops (Afzal et al., 2010; Muhammad, 2006 and Gwinn, et al., 2022). Additionally, Williamson et al. (2007) reported that *Botrytis cinerea* induces grey mold diseases in sunflowers, adversely affecting seed germination and seedling vigour. This finding highlights the vulnerability of farmer-saved seeds, particularly as storage duration extends, and emphasizes the necessity for improved storage practices for these seeds.

Interaction between Packaging Materials, Seed Source and Storage Duration

The interaction between packaging materials, seed source, and storage duration significantly affected seed moisture content. The differences in moisture content across packaging types and seed sources illustrate the critical role of both factors in maintaining seed quality, Gebeyaw, 2020; Suleiman et al., 2013). The lowest moisture content in QDS and certified seeds stored in plastic containers indicates effective moisture management, which is crucial for prolonging seed viability (Musebe et al., 2020) and Asante, et al., 2024)

However, the lack of significant interaction effects on germination percentage and seedling vigour index suggests that these outcomes may be more consistently influenced by individual factors rather than their combinations. In terms of fungal infection incidence, the interaction was significant, with the highest rates in farmer-saved seeds packed in sisal bags (Taban, 2017 and Yewle et al., 2024). This underscores the dual challenge of both selecting appropriate seed sources and using effective packaging to minimize fungal risks.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, this study highlights the critical role of packaging materials and storage duration in maintaining the viability and vigour of sunflower seeds. The findings demonstrate that plastic containers significantly enhance seed quality over time, preserving germination potential, seedling vigour, and

minimizing fungal infections compared to polypropylene and sisal bags. While seed source showed varying impacts on moisture content and fungal incidence, the interaction effects of packaging and storage duration were particularly pronounced. These results underscore the importance of selecting appropriate packaging methods and storage conditions to optimize seed quality, which is vital for improving sunflower productivity in Tanzania. Future research could further explore the long-term implications of these findings and develop best practices for seed storage in diverse agricultural contexts.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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Conflict of Interests

No any of the authors of this work have conflicting interest.

Authors' Contributions

SS, RM and YN designed the research study, SS carried out the experiment, gathered, processed, and analysed the experimental data and drafted the Manuscript. RM and YN supervised the entire implementation process, reviewed and edited the Manuscript.

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